

**THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES OF
PARENCHYMATOUS ORGANS DUE TO THE INFLUENCE
OF ETHANOL AND ENERGETIC DRINKS**

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ABSTRACT

Alcohol is ingested through the digestive tract. Unlike other nutrients, alcohol is injected directly into the blood through the gastric mucosa, as well as in the small intestine. Although alcohol metabolism occurs mainly in the liver, it can also be metabolized through other cells of the body. Alcohol is converted into a toxic chemical called acetaldehyde.

The effect of energetic drinks encourages a person to increase the dose: first the excitability occurs, then sharply decreases, and as a result the person thinks that he needs another energy drink. "Dependence" has a complex effect, as if a person feels more refreshed and seems that the desire to live has increased after consuming energetic drink

Chemical and biological dependence can also occur due to the high content of glucose in energy drinks.

Relevance of the problem. Firstly, regular consumption of alcoholic drinks causes acute and chronic pancreatitis. Patients with pancreatitis are 8 times more likely to develop pancreatic cancer than people without pancreatitis. Pancreatitis can lead to the failure of organs such as the heart, lungs and kidneys. The fact that the risk of pancreatitis-related death accounts for 2 to 10% of all cases means that the topic is relevant.

Secondly, the urgency of the problem is that in recent years it is important to develop optimal methods for diagnosing and predicting the pathomorphological processes that occur against the background of morphofunctional changes

in parenchymal organs under the influence of energetic drinks.

The pancreas is a complex organ that performs exocrine and endocrine functions and produces five hormones, including glucagon, insulin, somatostatin, ghrelin, and pancreatic polypeptide [23]. Insulin plays an important role in maintaining plasma glucose levels in a relatively narrow range throughout the day [24]. Morphological studies of the pancreas are mainly focused on acinar and islet cells, with less attention paid to the epithelium of the pancreatic ducts [25, 26, 27].

Alcoholic damage to the pancreas is manifested in the case of acute and chronic pancreatitis. Morphological signs of alcoholic damage to the pancreas were

identified. Ultrasound examination of pancreatic biopsy specimens in patients with exacerbation of chronic pancreatitis reveals the presence of aggregates of interstitial filaments in the pancreatic ducts and acinar cells [2].

Under the influence of alcohol, the exocrine function of the pancreas decreases, so does the secretion of water and bicarbonate. Due to the decrease in the volume of the liquid part of the pancreatic secretion, there is an increase in its viscosity and the precipitation of the proteins. Protein precipitates lead to narrowing of the glandular pathways and then to their complete obstruction. Increased excretion of free radical oxidation products of peroxide compounds and fatty acids in the bile, which easily enter the pancreatic duct in the presence of duodeno-pancreatic reflux, enhances the inflammatory process and contributes to the formation of calcification [4].

In chronic alcoholic pancreatitis, the gland becomes smaller and denser. Fibrous tissue appears as single or multiple cysts, and calcinates are detected in large ducts [6].

Swelling and necrosis of glandular tissue, and even total damage to the excitatory features of chronic pancreatitis, which developed after alcohol consumption, have been observed. According to the observations, the feature of microscopic changes in the pancreas in alcoholic disease is both focal and diffuse in nature. In addition to abruptly altered segments, there are also intact (intact) segments, and the ratio between parenchyma and stroma varies [5].

In alcoholic pancreatitis, fibrous components increase in the gland; acinar cells and islet apparatus become atrophic, often containing lipid deposits. The islands

of Langergans are unevenly distributed. Protein plugs, sometimes microcalcifications, are found in the canals. Ductal epithelium with atrophic or proliferative foci (proximal tumors of the ductal epithelium), necrosis of glandular tissue by the reaction of polymorphonuclear leukocytes, and cysts covered with cuboidal epithelium occur [1]. Acute pancreatitis is most often observed in young people, occurs immediately after ethanol poisoning, and is characterized by fatal total pancreatic necrosis. The development of acute pancreatitis in patients with alcoholism is mainly associated with hypersecretion, intravascular hypertension, and duodenoreflux to the pancreatic ducts that occur after alcohol consumption [3].

Chronic pancreatitis caused by alcohol is classified into several morphological forms: calcified, fibrous-indurative, obstructive, cystic [4].

The origin of chronic pancreatitis with alcohol is as follows: acute attacks of acute damage to the pancreas lead to recurrent attacks and fibrosis of the acinus.

With repeated follow-up of acute pancreatitis, morphological changes in the pancreas are exacerbated. Chronic pancreatic changes are less common in patients with mild primary exposure. However, even in the individual observation of acute alcoholic pancreatitis, it can lead to chronic morphological changes [29].

Complications associated with acute and chronic pancreatitis, including scarring of the pancreatic tissue and irreversible damage, reduce its effectiveness, leading to other problems, including malnutrition, impaired glucose metabolism, and chronic

pancreatitis associated with diabetes mellitus, which is difficult to treat. [28].

According to the statistics, the consumption of energy drinks has risen sharply over the past two decades [17]. Advertising of energy drinks with different labels on digital and social networks will further increase the interest of consumers in the products. Many different ingredients in energy drinks have different effects on different organs and systems, among which caffeine and guarin are the most toxic compounds for the body.

Adverse effects on the liver and kidneys were observed with significant changes in the structure of the liver and kidneys [21]. Chronic overuse of these beverages, especially by adolescents, can lead to poor sleep, worsening of school performance, frequent headaches, and depressive symptoms. They consume energy drinks to improve their athletic performance and efficiency, which enhances their sense of impact [22].

The classic composition of an energy drink is water, sugar, various amounts of caffeine, some biologically active compounds [7], such as guarana, glucuronolactone and taurine, various types of vitamin B [8].

Caffeine is a phytochemical widely used in the pharmaceutical and beverage industries. It is a central stimulant that has an effect on the nervous system by acting against adenosine receptors [9].

According to some scientists, the consumption of energy drinks increases mental alertness and slows down the feeling of fatigue, which may justify the effect of these drinks [10].

The glucose component in energy drinks is usually responsible for providing the substrate needed for physiological energy.

They are also associated with effects on the autonomic nervous system. There is ample evidence of a significant increase in heart rate and blood pressure after consuming energy drinks [11].

Another important ingredient in energy drinks is the sulfur-free amino acid taurine. It is present in sufficient amounts in a regularly balanced diet and can lead to cardiac arrhythmias. Disorders of taurine homeostasis associated with potentially harmful effects on the human brain, heart and skeletal system are identified [12].

Neurological deficits can be as insignificant as mood swings, and behavioral disorders can be as complex as epilepsy [13]. and autism associated with taurine imbalance in the body is observed. [14]. Some information about the damage to various organs of the body, including the pancreas as a result of oxidative stress is given [16].

Prolonged exposure of the organ to any inflammatory mediator in energy drinks cannot be stopped by its parenchyma and therefore may lead to fibrosis [19].

Damage from free radicals resulting from reactive oxygen species shows clear signs of apoptosis, including decreased cell volume and swelling of the cell membrane, indicating harmful effects associated with oxidative stress [20,30,31].

Some studies have shown that morpho-functional disorders of the pancreas have been observed after consumption of caffeinated beverages, and especially functional disorders of the exocrine and endocrine parts of the pancreas [5].

An analysis of the scientific literature suggests that as the trend of caffeinated beverages is on the rise among today's younger generation, there is a need to determine if the various organs of the body is adversely affected. At present, little is

known about the morphofunctional changes in the toxic effects of energy drinks on parenchymal tissue. There are

almost no data on the morphological changes of ethyl alcohol and energy drinks in rats during postnatal ontogenesis.

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